

Crystal engineering – retrospect and prospect[†]

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Introduction and historical

Crystal engineering or the design of organic solids is a rapidly emerging area in materials science today. Crystal engineering is one of the 'soft' areas in materials science and has emerged as an important cross-disciplinary field of basic and applied endeavour. It is of interest to trace the historical development of this subject¹. In a recent article, crystal engineering is described in the following way :

It was born (or at least christened) in 1971, had a difficult childhood, was delinquent, scandalous and making poor progress in 1988, was confirmed in 1989, and entered puberty in 1996. It now hovers on the edge of maturity, a scientific discipline establishing its own unique identity, developing a distinctive profile and with a promising future ahead. At the moment, its future appears meteoric.

Researchers and those familiar with the crystal engineering literature, will find no problem in identifying, from the above quotation, the christening of the subject by Schmidt² through his study of topochemical reactions, the well-known *Nature* editorial by Maddox³, in which he deplored the lack of progress in the field of crystal structure prediction, the publication of the first and still the only single author monograph on crystal engineering by Desiraju⁴ and the first ever conference solely devoted to the subject held in Digby, Nova Scotia. The continuing growth and impact of this subject is revealed by the appearance of three journals particular to the area – *Crystal Engineering* was launched by Elsevier in 1998, *CrystEngComm* by the Royal Society of Chemistry in 1999 and *Crystal Growth & Design* by the American Chemical Society in 2001.

The design of organic solids with specific physical and chemical properties encompasses a wide variety of research activity ranging from the understanding of crystal packing in organic molecular solids to the construction of open network structures based on metal-ligand coordination bonds, the so-called coordination polymers. On the one hand, one is able to analyse and understand with increasing certainty the vast amounts of accurate crystallographic data currently available from databases, while on the other, an apprecia-

tion of a phenomenon like polymorphism can lead to immediate benefits in applied areas, such as pharmaceutical development. The term 'crystal engineering' is, therefore, interpreted today in various ways and the scope of the present article is somewhat subjective.

Methodology

A major conceptual advance in the practice of crystal engineering came about in the early 1990s with the awareness that a crystal is one of the finest examples of a supramolecular entity⁵. This growing awareness brought crystal engineering within the mainstream of organic chemistry. Crystal engineering is recognised today as an important form of supramolecular synthesis and, as in any other form of synthesis, the scientific activity may be divided into matters of methodology and strategy. Broadly speaking, strategy deals with the synthetic plan of attack, while methodology deals with the ways in which this plan is executed.

In the supramolecular and crystal engineering context, methodology refers to an understanding of the properties of various intermolecular interactions. The crystal structure of a molecule is a free energy minimum resulting from the optimisation of attractive and repulsive intermolecular interactions with varying strengths, directional preferences and distance-dependence properties. Therefore, understanding the nature, strength and directionalities of intermolecular interactions is of fundamental importance. Intermolecular interactions in organic compounds are of two types : isotropic, medium-range forces that define the shape, size and close packing; anisotropic long-range forces which are electrostatic and include hydrogen bonds and heteroatom interactions⁶. The observed three-dimensional architecture in the crystal is the result then of the interplay between the demands of the isotropic van der Waals forces whose magnitude is proportional to the size of the molecule, and the anisotropic hydrogen bond interactions whose strengths are related to donor atom acidities and acceptor group basicities. These demands act sometimes in concert and at others in conflict; in the latter event, crystal structure are difficult

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Fig. 1

to predict and the likelihood of polymorphism could increase. However, it is through the similar preferences of isotropic and anisotropic interactions for inversion and screw/glide symmetries that most organic crystal structures achieve efficient close-packing. So, hydrogen bonded solids are not as a rule less densely packed than say, hydrocarbons. In this respect, organic crystals differ from inorganic ones where packing efficiency is obtained at the expense of coordination directionality or vice versa.

Hydrogen bonding is by far the most important intermolecular interaction in crystal engineering⁷. This is because, the interaction combines strength with directionality. As stated above, any crystal structure is the result of a balance or compromise between several types of interactions. If one of the interactions is strong and directional it is likely to dominate the packing and crystal structure prediction becomes easier. The stronger and more directional a particular interaction, the more distinctly it stands out among the others, and the more specifically efficient it becomes in controlling crystal packing. So typically, crystal engineering can proceed in two steps: (i) obtain an approximate hierarchy of interaction effectiveness; (ii) use this information to identify and suitably extend a family of compounds, in which a repetitive pattern occurs. This is the classical approach to crystal engineering and justifies its description as a new form of synthetic chemistry.

Traditional or conventional hydrogen bonds are typically of the O-H...O, N-H...O and N-H...N varieties, being constituted with the electronegative atoms O and N. In recent years, it has been recognised that hydrogen bonds may also be constituted between atoms or moieties of lesser electronegativity⁸. The importance and frequency of C-H...O interactions have been described in detail. It is clear that, although these interactions are individually weaker than O-H...O and N-H...O interactions, they are both long-range and directional and can, thus play an important part in design strategies for new materials. Take for instance, the crystal structure of the 1 : 1 molecular complex of 4-nitrobenzoic acid and 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)benzoic acid⁹. This structure is in the form of a linear ribbon, that is stabilised by noncentrosymmetric O-H...O and C-H...O dimers (Fig. 1). What is of significance here is that the formation of the O-H...O dimer in the structure does not preclude the formation of the C-H...O dimer. The strong and weak hydrogen bonds in this structure are said to be *insulated*¹⁰. Insulation is a very valuable attribute in crystal structure design because the levels of predictabil-

ity of a new structure rise with increasing levels of insulation. Crystal structure may also be engineered with weak hydrogen bonds only. In these cases, one might have to take

Fig. 2

recourse to multi-point recognition. Consider for instance, the molecular complex formed between 2,5-dibenzylidene-cyclopentanone and 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene (Fig. 2). In this structure, there are three C-H...O hydrogen bonds formed between the two molecular components and it is the three-point recognition that favours and establishes the stability of this pattern, for it is formed in a number of related complexes formed by 1,3,5-trinitrobenzene¹¹.

Strategy

Any plan of supramolecular synthesis must take into account the strengths, directionalities and distance-dependence properties of intermolecular interactions. A given molecule contains, in principle, several functional groups. Molecular recognition being a complementary phenomenon, interactions between functional groups can become quite specific for a given molecule. Accordingly, it may become quite difficult to anticipate crystal structures of even moderately complex molecules.

In the process of analysing crystal structures in terms of intermolecular interactions, one recognises certain repetitive structural units. These are typically small in size, are composed of specific functionalities and their resulting interactions are arranged in specific ways. The identification of these structural units is somewhat subjective but they are important in the sense that they may be associated with particular crystal packing characteristics. These units are approximations of actual crystal structures and they are much closer to real structures than say, molecular functional groups or even single interactions. Considering the importance of these units in the process of building up a crystal structure from its components, these units have been termed *supramolecular synthons*¹². Illustrated below is the relationship between a molecule, a functional group and the su-

pramolecular synthon that is derived from the functional group (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3

A desirable attribute of a supramolecular synthon is the property of *robustness*, in other words, the likelihood that it can be formed in many crystal structures. Identification of robust synthons greatly facilitates the synthetic aspects of the crystal engineering process. Designing a crystal structure effectively becomes then synthon design, and this in turn, is only possible from a proper knowledge of the pertinent intermolecular interactions. With reference to the example illustrated above, the use of the carboxy dimer synthon is shown with reference to both benzoic acid and terephthalic acid. The carboxy synthon is one of the most robust of structural elements, being formed by nearly a third of all carboxylic acids in the Cambridge Structural Database¹³. If only simple aromatic carboxylic acids are considered, the likelihood of occurrence of the carboxy dimer synthon goes up to almost 90%. Clearly, this synthon may be used regularly and reliably in crystal design.

As in molecular chemistry, an inherent advantage of the synthon concept in crystal engineering is that it can lead naturally to retrosynthetic thinking. Analysis of the often complex interplay between close packing, hydrogen bonding and other interactions in crystal structures may be termed *supramolecular retrosynthesis* and, insofar as analysis and synthesis are carried out in opposite senses, the term *retrosynthesis* aptly describes the procedure for logical analysis of a crystal structure. Consider, for instance, the crystal structure of 4-iodonitrobenzene which is based upon the NO₂...I synthon in itself constituted with two polarisation-based O...I interactions (Fig. 4). Here, the synthons are connected with spacer phenyl rings to give a ribbon structure. If the sense of the synthon alternates in the ribbon, the

Fig. 4

result is the crystal structure of 1 : 1 complex of 1,4-diiodobenzene and 1,4-dinitrobenzene. If the spacer is changed to a biphenyl moiety, the non-centrosymmetric structure of 4-iodo-4'-nitrobiphenyl is obtained¹⁴.

Applications

The design of organic non-linear optical (NLO) materials is an intensely active area of contemporary materials research. The development of photonic materials exhibiting technologically useful and accessible second-order (χ) phenomena such as second harmonic generation (SHG), has been particularly prominent. The initial approach to the production of materials with high χ values – namely, the synthesis and powder testing of assemblies of dipolar molecules with high molecular hyperpolarisabilities β – has now been superseded by more engineering type approaches which aim to predict how molecules pack or self-assemble in the crystalline state, thus providing some clues to the resulting solid-state properties of the materials. Recent theoretical advances in chromophore design, for example, the design of octupolar (zero dipole moment) molecules, have opened up new avenues for potential exploration by synthetic chemists¹⁵.

The challenge in designing an octupolar NLO solid is simple to visualise (Fig. 5) but difficult to solve experimentally. Can a trigonal molecule such as **1** be induced to form a stacked dimer such as **2**, which in turn will align two-dimensionally as in **3**, and three-dimensionally as in the non-centrosymmetric **4**, rather than the centrosymmetric **5**? The reason why one seeks out structures like **4** rather than **5** is because a solid can display NLO properties such as SHG, which is important in optical communication technologies, only if it lacks a centre of symmetry. The molecule of choice is 2,4,6-tris-(4-methylphenoxy)-1,3,5-triazine, which readily yields the two-dimensional pattern **3**. But the crucial step in the design sequence here is the alignment of the two-dimensional pattern **3** into the non-centrosymmetric **4**. This alignment is made possible by the mediation of very weak but directionally specific C–H... π interactions formed be-

Fig. 5

tween the methyl groups of the triazine and phenyl groups of the adjacent molecule in the crystal¹⁶. The C-H... π hydrogen bonds spiral around a threefold screw axis, with the result that the molecular threefold symmetry of the triazine is conserved in the crystal, a rare and unexpected occurrence.

Crystal engineering was originally concerned with the design of molecular solids only. During the last decade, the scope of the subject has been expanded to cover coordination polymers, substances that are formed by the interaction of polydentate ligands and transition metal ions to give divergent architectures¹⁷. The main advantage with coordination polymers vis-a-vis molecular crystals is that the connecting interactions are much stronger than those in neutral organic molecules. Therefore, levels of robustness and insulation are very high making structure predictability correspondingly more reliable. Coordination polymers can have open structures and are, therefore, capable of including guest molecules. They may, therefore, also be referred to as *nanoporous* solids.

The design of nanoporous solids (both organic and inorganic) with controlled sizes, shapes and chemical environments using the principles of crystal engineering has generated enormous interest in recent years because such designer solids may be exploited for separations, shape selective catalysis, and optoelectronic applications. In general, strategies for the synthesis of porous solids rely upon propagation of molecular symmetry into crystalline symmetry through rigid directional forces (hydrogen bonds and/or metal coordination bonds) such that an open porous net-

work may result. The flip side of this strategy is that such open networks always tend to interpenetrate. Despite these hurdles, a number of open porous networks have been constructed¹⁸.

Probably the most commercially significant aspect of crystal engineering lies in the study of polymorphic substances. Polymorphism is defined as a phenomenon wherein the same chemical substance exists in different crystalline forms. There is much interest in this well-known, though little understood, phenomenon¹⁹. Polymorphism is of immediate concern to the pharmaceutical industry while filing patent applications, because different forms of the same drug can exhibit widely different solubility and bioavailability properties. A polymorph of a drug is a different legal entity and is, therefore, entitled to independent patent protection. This is what renders the whole subject to be of commercial interest. ZantacTM is arguably the world's most successful drug. For a decade, it was the world's biggest selling pharmaceutical. The structure of this anti-ulcer drug is given above and the commercial form is the chloride salt of the protonated base. The crystal structure shows a tight hydrogen bonded ion-pair with no repeating structural patterns. This combination of a tight ion-pair with a lack of strong directional intermolecular hydrogen bonds is one ideal for the formation of polymorphs. The original patents in ranitidine chloride, the so-called Form-1, were owned by Glaxo-Wellcome. In 1996, the annual sales of the drug were £2,200,000,000, representing 24% of Glaxo-Wellcome's total sales. Glaxo subsequently filed for a second patent on a polymorph of the drug, the so-called Form-2. As soon as the original patent on Form-1 expired, Novopharm, a Canadian pharmaceutical company, planned to market Form-1. Glaxo-Wellcome filed suit against Novopharm claiming that it was not possible to manufacture pure Form-1 and that any process would result in some Form-2 being present, thus infringing Glaxo-Wellcome's second patent. The court found in favour of Novopharm. It is clear from these events, that no pharmaceutical company or, indeed, any chemical producer, can afford to ignore the importance of polymorphism or crystal engineering again. As polymorphs are now established in law as discrete materials, the consequences of structural purity are clear. The need for the characterisation of bulk materials as well as single crystals is unambiguously demonstrated and the advantages of control over structural form are also obvious.

The Future

A new field generally announces its appearance suddenly with a few key publications. Subsequent activity is often frantic with a large number of scientists getting in to

the fray. This so-called 'bandwagon effect' is common in science and crystal engineering is no exception. During this phase, good work continues to appear along with some indifferent contributions that get lost sooner or later. Some faddishness is inevitable. Crystal engineering might be considered as being in this frantic phase today. Almost surely, the present levels of activity will come down but if the field establishes itself as being of long-term value, the plateau level could still be quite high. It remains to be seen if crystal engineering will, thus, sustain itself in the future or not. However, many present indicators are very positive. The subject has implications in several mainstream areas – organic chemistry, inorganic chemistry, supramolecular chemistry, X-ray crystallography, materials research, computational chemistry and pharmaceutical chemistry. As crystal engineering moves from structure design to property design, its usefulness is bound to increase and with this its chances for longterm viability.

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